

Team Science “Toolkits”: A Resource List

By Kayleigh Ward, ESIIL | May 6, 2026

The ESIIL Team Science team has compiled this list of “toolkits” to help teams and individuals who are trying to learn and navigate the team science landscape as an applied practice. This list is of course not exhaustive, but provides some of the key, respected toolkits, worksheets, and guides for team science. We also recommend those just getting into team science to check out the International Network of Science of Team Science’s (INSciTS) educational resources.

Toolkits for team science vary across a spectrum of educational materials, facilitation guides and trainings. The ones covered here are free, open-access resources. In this resource guide you will find a table of items such as:

- Field guides for general use,
- CTSA collaboration-planning worksheets for teams projects (and teaming in general),
- Resources for novices and community organizations,
- Online training platforms for researchers and trainees, and
- Institution toolkits that address inclusion, authorship, and promotion/tenure in collaborative science.

We have not appended these resources here, such as full documents, as we encourage you to directly explore these resources at their associated agencies, organizations or institutions. As a highlight, the ESIIL Team Science team recommends five different key sources/groups, also provided in the table on the next page. These include:

1. **The National Cancer Institute’s** Collaboration and Team Science Field Guide and Team Science Toolkit (note: the toolkit is under maintenance and may not be accessible as of May, 2026).
2. **Northwestern University’s** COALESCE project at teamscience.net. The COALESCE project is particularly useful from a community standpoint and for anyone doing community engaged research (instead of just with scientific teams). This is also the best resource for those outside biomedical, clinical and health fields.
3. **The University of Texas Medical Branch’s** TeamMAPPS training modules at <https://teammapps.utmb.edu/>

4. **University of Wisconsin Madison’s** Institute for Clinical and Translational Research at <https://ictr.wisc.edu/>. The ICTR has excellent worksheets available, as does UNC.
5. **The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill** Translational and Clinical Sciences Institute (TraCS) at <https://tracs.unc.edu/>.

Resource Table

Item...	Author(s)...	Scope and its intended users...	Website/Document link...
Collaboration and Team Science Field Guide	National Cancer Institute at NIH	Broad practical guide for researchers considering, joining, or leading collaborative research teams across the continuum from looser collaborations to integrated teams.	https://www.cancer.gov/about-nci/organization/crs/research-initiatives/team-science-field-guide/collaboration-team-science-guide.pdf
Team Science Toolkit	NCI Division of Cancer Control and Population Sciences, Behavioral Research Program	Official NCI portal supporting the practice and study of team science for people who manage, support, conduct, or evaluate team-based research. <i>**This item is currently under maintenance</i>	https://cancercontrol.cancer.gov/brp/research/team-science-toolkit
COALESCE / TeamScience.net	Northwestern University	Open-access team science e-learning for researchers, trainees, and health/medical professionals working across disciplines.	https://www.teamscience.net/
Team Science Community Toolkit	Northwestern University	Community-engaged research toolkit designed primarily for community organizations and academic partners deciding whether and how to collaborate, but explicitly framed as applicable more broadly.	https://www.teamscience.net/home/resources
Team Science Toolkit	Penn State Clinical and Translational Science Institute	Web “toolbox” designed especially for novices of team science and for teams moving through the research lifecycle.	https://ctsi.psu.edu/services/toolkits/team-science/overview
UW-ICTR Collaboration Planning Worksheet Template	University of Wisconsin–Madison Institute for Clinical and Translational Research (Team Science Core)	A practical and excellent worksheet for translational/interdisciplinary teams or for facilitating collaboration-planning sessions.	https://ictr.wisc.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Collaboration-Planning-Worksheet-Template-2026.pdf

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Team Science Collaboration Planning Worksheet	UNC-Chapel Hill TraCS Team Science	Worksheet supporting facilitated collaboration planning for new or existing multidisciplinary/translational research teams.	https://tracs.unc.edu/docs/team-science/TraCS_Team_Science_Collaboration_Planning_Worksheet_March_2025.pdf
TeamMAPPS	University of Texas Medical Branch School of Nursing / Institute for Translational Sciences	Skills training for scientists, students, and scientific teams; especially relevant to translational teams and CTSA-oriented settings.	https://teammapps.utmb.edu/
Interprofessional Team Writing Toolkit	University of Washington Center for Health Sciences Interprofessional Education, Research & Practice	For IPE researchers of all levels who need to collaborate on writing across professions and disciplines. This is especially useful for those who haven't done more complex collaborative writing.	https://collaborate.uw.edu/team-science/interprofessional-team-writing-toolkit/
Appointment, Promotion, and Tenure Toolkit	University of Washington Institute for Translational Health Sciences Team Science Core and colleagues	Institutional toolkit for early-career faculty, department chairs, and committees to recognize and reward interdisciplinary/team-science work. While this is particular to the University of Washington, it is a nice guidebook for recognizing collaborative work.	https://collaborate.uw.edu/team-science/appointment-promotion-and-tenure-apt-toolkit/
CREDITS Collaboration Toolkit	Center for Research, Excellence, and Diversity in Team Scholarship (CREDITS), UCSB	A collaboration toolkit and framework for research development professionals and collaborative team members, with emphasis on inclusive team environments and institutional change. CREDITS also has an expanded list of resources and other guides that would be of interest to any team member, team science practitioner and/or scientist. They especially have some nice resources on diversity and equity in teams.	https://credits.ucsb.edu/inclusive-collaboration-toolkit/

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